

Low-Power Class-C VCO in SiGe BiCMOS With Varactor Embedded in Cross-Feedback Path for Tuning Range Enhancement

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Abstract—The tuning range (TR) of LC voltage-controlled oscillators (VCOs) is primarily limited by the maximum tuning ratio of varactors in a given process, and significantly degraded by parasitic capacitance of the transistors in a cross-feedback path especially for millimeter-wave (mm-wave) VCOs. In this paper, a mm-wave class-C VCO is demonstrated in SiGe BiCMOS technology, with varactors embedded in the cross-feedback path to enhance the TR. Equivalent circuit model and derived analytical expressions show that in the presence of large parasitic capacitance at the base of the transistors, introducing varactors in the cross-feedback path significantly improves the overall TR. Therefore, the TR limitation by varactor tuning ratio can be released. Analysis of startup and phase noise with consideration of base parasitics and practical values of cross-feedback capacitance are given to replenish the conventional class-C analysis and methodology. Based on the analysis, a VCO containing varactors both in the LC -tank and the cross-feedback path is proposed to achieve a continuous TR from 29.6 GHz to 32.4 GHz, low DC power consumption of 10.1 mW, and low phase noise of -114.6 dBc/Hz at 10-MHz offset in measurements.

Index Terms—Bipolar complementary metal-oxide-semiconductor (BiCMOS), class-C, cross-coupled pair, Ka -band, low power, metal-oxide-metal (MOM) capacitor, millimeter-wave, phase noise, silicon-germanium (SiGe), startup, tuning range, varactor, voltage-controlled oscillator.

I. INTRODUCTION

ADVANCED silicon-based technologies with increasing f_T and f_{max} enable the implementation of high-performance millimeter-wave (mm-wave) transceivers, especially the beyond-5G or 6G subterahertz systems. These systems employ frequency synthesizers that integrate frequency multipliers and dividers to generate the desired operating frequencies from a single local oscillator (LO). This approach leverages LO generation to achieve a broad tuning range (TR), low DC power, and minimal phase noise, thereby enhancing the overall system performance and efficiency.

The recent literature has proposed different designs and techniques to meet such requirements. For example, [1] demonstrates a differential Colpitts oscillator in SiGe BiCMOS

with a center frequency of 31.6 GHz. Although being favored for low phase noise of this topology, the proposed oscillator requires additional circuitry for biasing as generally occurring in conventional Colpitts oscillators [2], and therefore, the design complexity is increased. In [3] and [4], the prevalent class-B oscillator topology is utilized in CMOS to address the frequency band of 28.3 GHz and 32.2 GHz, respectively. Both designs introduce an additional LC network at the tail-current source for noise filtering to improve the phase-noise performance, whereas the chip area is increased, and delicate design of the LC is required which is sensitive to parasitics.

Compared to the class-B oscillators, the class-C topology is more power-efficient for the same phase-noise level by enforcing the cross-coupled transistor pair of the class-B oscillator to operate in class-C [5], [6]. A class-C oscillator in SiGe BiCMOS is proposed in [7] for the applications at 25 GHz with relatively low phase noise and high efficiency. However, its TR is limited by the parasitic capacitance in parallel to the varactors in the LC -tank. In fact, in addition to the parasitic capacitance at the collector node of the cross-coupled pair, the parasitic capacitance at the base node also greatly affects the TR as analyzed in Section II.

Another relevant factor that primarily limits the TR is the maximum tuning ratio of the varactor in a given technology, denoted as C_{max}/C_{min} . For example, in the given SiGe BiCMOS technology, the maximum C_{max}/C_{min} of the available heterojunction bipolar transistors (HBTs) connected as a varactor is 1.2, obtained by applying a tuning voltage across the base-collector junction under nonbreakdown condition. It leads to a theoretical TR of 9.1% in a voltage-controlled oscillator (VCO) without any parasitic capacitances. This value will further reduce in practical designs, and hence, the TR of a VCO becomes insufficient for various applications. Using switch-based digital capacitor banks is an option to enhance the TR [8]–[10]. However, this method requires additional digital control circuitry and the tuning of the oscillation frequency is discrete. Therefore, it is essential to figure out new design approaches to improve the TR for a given varactor C_{max}/C_{min} .

In this paper, a class-C VCO is proposed to achieve a continuous TR from 29.6 GHz to 32.4 GHz, *i.e.* 9.03%, with very low DC power consumption of 10.1 mW and low phase noise of -114.6 dBc/Hz at 10-MHz offset in measurements. Derived analytical expressions and measurements indicate that replacing the fixed capacitors in the cross-feedback path with varactors can significantly address the issue of the parasitic

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Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of simplified class-C oscillator with varactors in the cross-feedback path, and (b) equivalent circuit of the cross-coupled pair. c_b denotes the parasitic capacitance at the base of the transistor.

capacitance at the base of the transistor, and release the TR limitation by the parasitic capacitance at the collector of the transistor. Furthermore, in the implementation a new varactor is proposed for its higher C_{max}/C_{min} . A specific capacitor placement in layout is presented for its symmetrical property and compactness.

II. CIRCUIT DESIGN

A. Concept of Varactor Embedded in the Cross-Feedback Path

A simplified schematic of a class-C oscillator with varactors in the cross-feedback path is shown in Fig. 1a. It consists of an LC-tank and a cross-coupled pair, composed of transistors, Q_1 and Q_2 , to generate sufficient negative resistance. Here, the quality factor of the LC-tank is assumed to be dominated by inductor losses characterized by the series resistance, $R_{s,L}$. Two pairs of varactors can be seen as C_{tank} in the LC-tank and C_f in the cross-feedback path. As mentioned before, the TR of VCOs is limited by C_{max}/C_{min} , and parasitic capacitances of the transistors in the cross-coupled pair. The parasitic capacitance to ground at the collector node of the transistor can be resolved into the tank capacitance, and therefore, degrades C_{max}/C_{min} of the LC-tank. Moreover, large parasitic capacitance at the base terminal, as shown as c_b , also affects the TR of the VCO by regulating the input admittance of the cross-coupled pair, denoted as Y_{in} in Fig. 1a.

To determine Y_{in} and analyze the effect of the parasitic capacitance at the base of the transistor, a small-signal equivalent circuit is plotted in Fig. 1b. The equivalent circuit of each transistor is composed of the input resistance, r_π , the base-collector capacitance, c_μ , and a voltage-controlled current

source, denoted as $g_m v_\pi$. Y_{in} is determined by the division of i_x by v_x , where

$$v_x = \frac{C_f}{C_f - c_\mu} (v_{\pi 1} - v_{\pi 2}) \left(1 + \frac{1}{j\omega C_f Z_\pi} + \frac{c_\mu}{C_f} \right), \quad (1)$$

$$i_x = \frac{1}{2} (v_{\pi 1} - v_{\pi 2}) \left(\frac{1}{Z_\pi} - g_m + 2j\omega c_\mu \right) + j\omega c_\mu v_x. \quad (2)$$

Z_π denotes the input impedance of a transistor in the equivalent circuit, given by

$$Z_\pi = \frac{r_\pi}{1 + j\omega r_\pi c_b}. \quad (3)$$

By assuming $g_m r_\pi \gg 1$, and $\omega^2 r_\pi^2 (C_f + c_b + c_\mu)^2 \gg 1$, it can be derived that

$$G_{in} = -\frac{g_m}{2} \frac{C_f - c_\mu}{C_f + c_b + c_\mu}, \quad (4)$$

$$B_{in} = \frac{C_f - c_\mu}{2(C_f + c_b + c_\mu)} \left[-\frac{g_m}{\omega r_\pi (C_f + c_b + c_\mu)} + \omega(c_b + 2c_\mu) \right] + \omega c_\mu. \quad (5)$$

If r_π is the dominant component compared to c_b at the transistor input, i.e., $Z_\pi \approx r_\pi$, and c_μ is negligible, Y_{in} for conventional class-C oscillators can be rewritten as

$$Y_{in} = -\frac{g_m}{2} - \frac{1}{2} j \frac{g_m}{\omega C_f r_\pi}. \quad (6)$$

This also indicates the same startup condition as class-B oscillators as seen from the real part of (6). The imaginary part is considerably small if r_π is in the k Ω range and C_f is in the pF range. As a result, the oscillation frequency of the VCO is mainly determined by the resonant frequency of the LC-tank.

On the other hand, when c_b is considerably large, the oscillation frequency now is determined by the LC-tank together with B_{in} according to (4) and (5) as expected. To clearly evaluate the relationships between the tuning ratio of the varactors in the LC-tank and in the cross-feedback path, the parasitic capacitance, c_b , and the TR of the VCO, Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b are plotted based on the analysis. Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b show the theoretical TR of the VCO in percentage, i.e., the fractional bandwidth (FBW), versus c_b and C_{max}/C_{min} of the tunable C_{tank} , and the tunable C_f , respectively. Fig. 2a indicates that as c_b increases, the TR of the VCO with only tunable C_{tank} is significantly reduced as expected in a typical VCO. On the other hand, the TR of the VCO with only tunable C_f shows the opposite when c_b increases. It suggests that with a certain parasitic capacitance, using two tunable elements, C_{tank} and C_f , has the possibility to improve the TR of the VCO.

Fig. 3 shows the TR of the VCO in percentage using the two tunable elements, i.e., C_{tank} and C_f , with three values of c_b as representatives. As can be seen the reduced TR of C_{tank} due to larger c_b can be released by tunable C_f . The theoretical TR improvement by C_f in percentage can be computed as shown in Fig. 4, where the same tuning ratio of C_{tank} and C_f varactors is employed. The TR can be improved in the presence of a considerably large c_b , e.g., by more than 15%

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2. Simulated VCO tuning FBW versus c_b , and C_{max}/C_{min} of (a) tunable C_{tank} , and (b) tunable C_f .

Fig. 3. Simulated VCO tuning FBW versus C_{max}/C_{min} of tunable C_{tank} and C_f with three different values of parasitic c_b .

with c_b of 100 fF, 40% with c_b of 200 fF, and 60% with c_b of 300 fF, respectively. Note that the tuning ratio of the C_{tank} and C_f varactors can be different.

For a given c_b , the improvement is more noticeable with very small C_{max}/C_{min} . It can be therefore concluded that in class-C VCOs, introducing a tunable C_f is beneficial for the TR in the circumstance of considerably large c_b , and simultaneously, very low tuning ratio of varactors in the process.

Fig. 4. Maximum improvement of FBW by second tunable element, C_f , with given varactor C_{max}/C_{min} .

B. Startup Considerations

Taking into account the base parasitics and cross-feedback capacitance, the negative conductance given by (4) has to compensate the losses of the LC -tank for startup of the VCO. Assuming that the quality factor of the inductor, Q_L , fulfills $Q_L^2 \gg 1$, the startup condition can be determined as

$$G_{in} + \frac{1}{R_{p,L}} \leq 0, \quad (7)$$

where

$$R_{p,L} \approx Q_L^2 R_{s,L}. \quad (8)$$

Combining (4), (7), and (8), and assuming c_μ negligible compared to C_f and c_b , the startup condition can be derived as

$$g_m \geq 2 \left(1 + \frac{c_b}{C_f} \right) \frac{1}{Q_L^2 R_{s,L}}. \quad (9)$$

This equation indicates the minimum transconductance requirement for a given cross-coupled pair with C_f and c_b , and a given LC -tank configuration. It can be simplified as the same equation reported in [11] if c_b is considerably smaller than C_f . Typically, a small capacitance ratio c_b/C_f and a large Q_L benefit the startup of the VCO. The minimum capacitance of the tunable C_f imposes the worst-case condition of startup.

g_m is associated with the transistor size, e.g., number of multipliers of the HBTs in the given SiGe BiCMOS technology, and the base bias, V_B , as shown in Fig. 5a. Reducing the number of multipliers intrinsically results in less collector and base parasitic capacitance, and therefore, improves the TR. Meanwhile, for a given g_m determined by (9), a higher base bias is required as indicated in Fig. 5a, leading to higher collector DC current, and hence, for a given power consumption, the supply voltage, V_{CC} , has to decrease. For low-power design, the difference between V_B and V_{CC} defines the minimum number of multipliers for a given g_m as the base-collector junction has to be reverse biased. For example, as shown in Fig. 5b, for a given g_m of 37 mS, the number of multipliers has to be selected above three such that the transistor is properly biased. It should be noted that sufficient startup margin has to be taken into account in (9) with regard to process, voltage, and temperature (PVT) variation.

Fig. 5. (a) Simulated g_m versus base bias of the HBTs with different numbers of multipliers, and (b) operating point of different numbers of multipliers for the same power consumption and $g_m = 37$ mS.

C. Phase Noise

According to the Leeson-Cutler phase-noise model [12], [13], the phase noise behavior in the $1/f^2$ region can be analyzed based on the closed-loop transfer function obtained from Fig. 6, as recently reported in [14]–[16]. Different from the RLC model proposed in [17] that considers the tank admittance as the only element to determine the oscillation frequency, in this model the imaginary part of the cross-coupled pair with c_b and C_f , shown as (5), is also included. The admittance of the parallel RLC network including B_{in} for an offset frequency, $\Delta\omega$, from the oscillation frequency, ω_o , is given by

$$Y(\omega_o + \Delta\omega) = \frac{1}{R_{p,L}} + \frac{1}{2}j(\omega_o + \Delta\omega)C_{tank} + \frac{1}{j(\omega_o + \Delta\omega)L} + jB_{in}(\omega_o + \Delta\omega), \quad (10)$$

where ω_o is determined by

$$\frac{1}{2}j\omega_o C_{tank} + \frac{1}{j\omega_o L} + jB_{in}(\omega_o) = 0. \quad (11)$$

The impedance of the parallel RLC network including B_{in} for $\Delta\omega \ll \omega_o$ can be calculated as

$$Z(\omega_o + \Delta\omega) = \frac{1}{Y(\omega_o + \Delta\omega)} \approx \frac{1}{G_{p,L}} \frac{1}{1 + j2Q \frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_o}}, \quad (12)$$

Fig. 6. RLC oscillator with tunable element in the active part.

Fig. 7. Small-signal half-circuit model of the VCO for phase noise analysis.

(12) is similar to the equation reported in [17], whereas now the quality factor of the parallel RLC network including B_{in} , Q , is given by

$$Q = \omega_o \left(\frac{1}{2}C_{tank} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{C_f c_b}{C_f + c_b} \right) R_{p,L}. \quad (13)$$

Note that in (13), increasing c_b does not obtain higher Q as shown obviously in the capacitance term, because Q is also related to the term ω_o which is simultaneously affected by c_b .

The closed-loop transfer function in Fig. 6, $H(\Delta\omega)$, for a parallel current source is therefore determined from (12) as

$$H(\Delta\omega) = -j \frac{1}{G_{p,L}} \frac{\omega_o}{2Q\Delta\omega}. \quad (14)$$

The phase noise spectrum in the $1/f^2$ region is given by

$$\mathcal{L}(\Delta\omega) = 10 \cdot \log \left(\frac{\overline{v_{noise}^2}}{v_{sig}^2} \right) = 10 \cdot \log \left(\frac{\frac{1}{2}|H(\Delta\omega)|^2 \sum_m \frac{i_{n,m}^2}{\Delta f}}{\frac{1}{2}V_{max}^2} \right), \quad (15)$$

where V_{max} is the maximum voltage swing across the LC -tank. The factor of $1/2$ in the numerator arises from neglecting the contribution of amplitude noise [17]. The $i_{n,m}^2/\Delta f$ terms denote the equivalent current noise spectral density due to the collector and base shot noise, inductor noise, and varactor noise. Fig. 7 shows a small-signal half-circuit model of the VCO highlighting the abovementioned noise sources as [18]. The equivalent current noise spectral density of $R_{p,L}/2$ in the half-circuit model is the same as that of $R_{p,L}$ in the complete LC -tank. Typically for advanced SiGe HBTs, the collector current noise spectral density is several orders of magnitude higher compared to the base current noise spectral density [19]. In addition, the dominance of collector shot noise

Fig. 8. Simulated phase noise with different parasitic c_b .

compared to inductor noise can be obtained from (8) and (9), *i.e.*,

$$\frac{I_C}{V_T} > \frac{2}{R_{p,L}}. \quad (16)$$

Therefore, we obtain

$$2qI_C > \frac{4kT}{R_{p,L}}, \quad (17)$$

where I_C is the quiescent collector current, and $V_T = kT/q$ in (16) is the thermal voltage of the transistor.

Now, by taking into account the collector shot noise and varactor noise into (15), we can obtain an insightful approximation for the phase noise as

$$\mathcal{L}(\Delta\omega) = 10 \cdot \log \left[\frac{R_{p,L} \left(\frac{\omega_o}{2Q\Delta\omega} \right)^2 \left(qI_C + \frac{2kT}{R_{C_f}} \right)}{P_s} \right], \quad (18)$$

where R_{C_f} is the effective parallel resistance of C_f , and $P_s = V_{max}^2/2R_{p,L}$ is the average power dissipated in the resistive part of the LC -tank.

According to (18), decreasing I_C and increasing R_{C_f} can improve the phase-noise performance of the VCO. The theoretical lowest phase noise can be estimated from the minimum required g_m given as (9). Also, a higher quality factor of C_f , *i.e.*, large R_{C_f} , is beneficial to the phase-noise performance. Moreover, with regard to (13), the phase noise of the VCO can be improved by having larger base parasitic, c_b . This is verified in simulations as shown in Fig. 8 with the test bench showcased and all lumped component values close to those of the implementation except for variable c_b . Four values of c_b are given as representatives and the phase noise decreases with increasing c_b . In addition, with considerably large c_b , a tunable C_{tank} has a stronger impact on Q and therefore, the phase noise at certain frequencies than a tunable C_f as indicated in (13) and (18).

D. Summary for Circuit Design

When the tunable C_f is embedded in the cross-feedback path, the optimum transistor size and the operating point of the cross-coupled pair can be determined at the minimum C_f to ensure that the VCO fulfills the startup condition. Moreover, phase noise is improved by having higher parasitic c_b and by decreasing the current I_C according to (13) and (18), whereas

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 9. (a) Schematic of the VCO including parasitics, (b) the proposed varactor topology, and (c) illustration of capacitor placement on topmost metal layer in layout. The corresponding capacitor surface in schematic and layout are denoted by the same color. The capacitor placement occupies an overall area of $0.34 \times 0.14 \text{ mm}^2$ in layout.

degrading g_m leads to startup difficulties according to (9). A high quality factor of C_f is beneficial for both startup and phase noise.

III. VCO IMPLEMENTATION

A. VCO Schematic

The schematic of the proposed VCO including parasitic capacitances is shown in Fig. 9a, where the varactor implementations are detailed in Fig. 9b. The circuit parameters and parasitic capacitances are given in Table I and Table II, respectively. The capacitance and inductance values are extracted from EM simulations in Keysight ADS and ADS Momentum. Varactors are introduced both in the cross-feedback path

TABLE I
CIRCUIT PARAMETERS AND VALUES

Parameter	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	L_{tank}
Value	320 fF	130 fF	40 fF	85 fF	11 fF	75 pH
Parameter	R_1	R_2	R_{bias}	C_{out}	L_{out}	
Value	2.5 k Ω	400 Ω	1 k Ω	180 fF	670 pH	

TABLE II
PARASITIC CAPACITANCES AND VALUES

Parameter	c_b	c_{par1}	c_{par2}	c_{par3}	c_{par4}	c_{par5}
Value	99.1 fF	117 fF	29.2 fF	12.5 fF	21.6 fF	3.4 fF

and LC-tank. The cross-coupled pair is composed of two transistors, denoted as Q_1 and Q_2 , two fixed capacitors in the cross-feedback path, C_1 , and two varactors. The combination of the fixed capacitor and the varactor in parallel can be treated as a C_f in Fig. 1a.

The fixed capacitors, C_1 , ensure class-C operation of the VCO at different tuning voltage settings. This however results in lower tuning ratio of C_f , and thus, a reduced TR of the VCO. Similarly, in the LC-tank the collector parasitic, c_{par1} , reduces the tuning ratio of C_{tank} . As mentioned before, the tuning ratio of the varactor, C_{max}/C_{min} , is limited to 1.2 in the given SiGe BiCMOS technology. Considering C_1 and c_{par1} , respectively, the tuning ratio of C_f and C_{tank} is further decreased. It is therefore required to design new varactors which provide sufficient C_{max}/C_{min} of C_f and C_{tank} and improves the TR of the VCO.

The varactor proposed in the design introduces the resistive voltage divider, R_1 and R_2 , for continuous frequency tuning compared to the conventional switched capacitor unit [20]. The working principle of the varactor is explained as follows. At different tuning voltage settings, Q_3 and Q_4 can be considered as an equivalent variable impedance. For instance, as shown in Fig. 10, at high tuning voltage settings of V_{t1} , the equivalent impedance of Q_3 , denoted as Z_3 , exhibits low series impedance, and the overall impedance of the varactor is dominated by C_2 and C_3 . On the other hand, at low tuning voltage settings, Q_3 presents high series impedance. As a result, c_{par2} and c_{par3} becomes more dominant to the overall impedance compared to the large series capacitances C_2 and C_3 . Q_3 is selected to have a multiplier of six in the implementation by considering the tradeoff between series resistance that limits the overall impedance of the varactor at high tuning voltage settings, and transistor parasitics that limit the overall impedance at low tuning voltage settings, respectively. Note that the parasitic capacitance between the collector and the emitter of the transistor can be neglected in the frequency band of interest.

The simulated input impedance of the varactor at different tuning voltage settings ranging from 0.6 V to 1.4 V is shown in Fig. 10 with $R_1 = 2.5$ k Ω and $R_2 = 400$ Ω . The equivalent

Fig. 10. Simulated input impedance of the varactor in C_f at 31 GHz with the equivalent circuit at high and low tuning voltage settings showcased. Tuning voltage ranges from 0.6 V to 1.4 V.

Fig. 11. (a) Simulated input impedance of the varactor in C_f at 31 GHz with $R_1 = 2.5$ k Ω and different R_2 , and (b) equivalent series capacitance of the varactor with $R_2 = 400$ Ω and different R_1/R_2 . The structure and performance of a traditional varactor configuration is shown for comparison.

series capacitance ranges from 11.9 fF at $V_{t1} = 0.6$ V to 30.3 fF at $V_{t1} = 1.4$ V. This results in a tuning ratio of 2.55 of the varactor itself. With the fixed C_1 of 320 fF in parallel, the tuning ratio of C_f of 1.06 is obtained. According to Fig. 4, this ratio corresponds to a FBW improvement of 17.5% assuming the same tuning ratio for C_{tank} . The simulated highest equivalent parallel resistance of the varactor is 530 Ω at $V_{t1} = 0.9$ V. This means that the minimum quality factor of C_f is above 34. Fig. 11a shows the impact of R_2 on the input impedance of the varactor in C_f with a fixed R_1 of 2.5 k Ω . The equivalent series capacitance at low tuning

voltage settings significantly increases for R_2 below 400 Ω leading to lower tuning ratio of the varactor. In addition, the R_1/R_2 -ratio controls the DC bias voltages of the transistor. Consequently, the capacitance versus tuning voltage profile, *i.e.* C - V curve of the varactor, changes as plotted in Fig. 11b with $R_2 = 400 \Omega$. The R_1/R_2 -ratio does not affect the tuning ratio of the varactor as $R_2 \geq 400 \Omega$ is selected which does not dominate the parasitic capacitances at low tuning voltage settings. The varactor consumes 1 mA of DC current at its highest tuning voltage setting merely from the resistive voltage divider. Increasing resistance can reduce the DC power consumption while keeping the varactor tuning ratio. The reason to take R_1 of 2.5 k Ω and R_2 of 400 Ω in this design is due to our available PDK.

Similarly in the LC -tank, Q_4 is selected to have a multiplier of six in the implementation. The equivalent series capacitance of the varactor in C_{tank} ranges from 6.1 fF to 9.7 fF in simulations with a tuning ratio of 1.6, and with the 117-fF c_{par1} in parallel, the resulted tuning ratio of C_{tank} is 1.03. Note that C_{tank} contains only c_{par1} as fixed tank capacitance. The minimum quality factor of C_{tank} is above 40 in simulations, and hence, the quality factor of the LC -tank is dominated by losses of the inductor.

The transistor size and operating point of Q_1 and Q_2 are determined based on Fig. 5. According to (9) and the parameter values from EM simulations, g_m should be higher than 18 mS with regard to the minimum C_f . Hence, Q_1 and Q_2 are selected to have a multiplier of four, and are biased at 0.83 V for the proposed VCO to provide sufficient startup margin of $g_m = 37$ mS taking into account PVT variations. The collector of the cross-coupled pair is also biased at 0.83 V for low-power operation. To drive 50- Ω terminations in the measurement environment, common-emitter buffers are designed consisting of Q_5 , Q_6 , C_{out} , and L_{out} . Q_5 and Q_6 also have a multiplier of four as Q_1 and Q_2 . The value of C_{out} and L_{out} are given in Table I.

B. Capacitor Placement

The layout of differential VCOs is required to have matched properties which significantly affect performance and robustness. Especially, for the proposed VCO, all denoted capacitors, *i.e.* C_{1-5} , should be included and implemented in a symmetrical way with straightforward wirings to the cross-coupled transistors Q_1 and Q_2 , and tuning transistors Q_3 and Q_4 . A symmetrical and compact capacitor placement is therefore proposed in Fig. 9c. In this implementation, interdigitated metal-oxide-metal (MOM) capacitors are designed on the topmost metal layer due to the lowest sheet resistance and parasitic capacitance to ground, with shielding on the bottommost metal layer for good isolation to the substrate. In each half circuit, C_1 , C_2 , and C_4 share a common surface which is implemented with a toothed shape identified in red color as shown in Fig. 9c. For good separation of the oscillator core and the tuning circuitry, the other surface of C_1 is located on the top of the layout identified in blue color, while the other surface of C_2 and C_4 are located at the bottom of the layout identified in green and purple color, respectively. The surface of C_3

Fig. 12. Simulated time-domain waveform of the collector current and voltage of Q_1 .

TABLE III
SIMULATION OF PVT VARIATIONS

Condition		Continuous TR (GHz)	FBW (%)	Phase noise ⁺ (dBc/Hz)
Process Variation	typ	28.69 - 31.71	10	-112.5
	wcs	30.90 - 32.24	4.2	-119.1
	bcs	28.09 - 31.36	11	-104.5
Voltage Variation	+10%	28.72 - 31.73	9.9	-111.9
	-10%	28.66 - 31.69	10	-113.1
Temperature	70°C	27.86 - 30.89	10.3	-98.6
	0°C	29.93 - 32.19	7.3	-115.7

⁺ At 10-MHz offset.

shared with C_1 extends at the edge of the layout, so that the other surface of C_3 identified in orange color can be directly connected to the tuning circuitry at the bottom of the layout. C_5 is also a MOM capacitor in the implementation placed outside of this capacitor placement.

The proposed capacitor placement includes most of the capacitors and, importantly, it allows the routing to the cross-coupled pair and tuning circuitry to be separated in space, increasing design robustness. Moreover, coupling between surfaces of the capacitors is reduced due to the common surface in the middle. The capacitance density is lower compared to MOM capacitors having multiple metal layers, whereas implementing if only on the topmost metal layer can significantly reduce the parasitic capacitance, and hence, mitigate the tuning ratio of the varactors. The capacitor placement occupies an overall area of $0.34 \times 0.14 \text{ mm}^2$ in layout.

C. Simulation and PVT Results

Fig. 12 shows the post-layout simulated time-domain waveform of the collector current and voltage of Q_1 with the supply and bias voltage at 0.83 V. The waveforms demonstrate the class-C operation of the VCO.

Simulations of different PVT conditions are carried out and the results are presented in Table III. It is shown that under PVT variations, the VCO can still operate but performance degradation is observed. For example, the FBW reduces under

Fig. 13. Chip photograph of the VCO under test. The total chip size including all pads is $0.72 \times 0.7 \text{ mm}^2$.

the worst-case (wcs) condition of the transistors and at low temperature.

IV. MEASUREMENT RESULTS

The proposed VCO is fabricated in the IHP 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS technology. A photograph of the chip under test is shown in Fig. 13. It occupies an area of 0.5 mm^2 including all measurement pads. Tuning voltages V_{t1} and V_{t2} are applied in the range of 0.6 V to 1.4 V. The bias voltage applied in measurements is 0.83 V. The VCO core and output buffer draws 5.4 mA and 6.2 mA from a 0.83-V DC power supply in measurements, respectively. Together with the varactors, the VCO core consumes a total of 4.5 mW of DC power at the lowest tuning voltage setting, and 10.1 mW at the highest tuning voltage setting.

The on-wafer measurement environment is set up with a Rohde & Schwarz FSW Signal & Spectrum Analyzer, and probe 40A-GSSG-100-N by GGB Industries Inc. One of the RF probes is connected to the input port of the spectrum analyzer, and the other RF probe is connected to a Keysight 901C $50\text{-}\Omega$ termination. The measured oscillation frequency under different tuning voltages is presented in Fig. 14a. Note that V_{t1} and V_{t2} are continuous tuning voltages for the varactors in the cross-feedback path and in the LC -tank, respectively. The measured TR of the VCO is from 29.6 GHz to 32.4 GHz. The TR contributed by the varactors in the cross-feedback path is 1.01 GHz with V_{t1} from 0.6 V to 1.4 V, and the TR controlled by the varactors in the LC -tank is 1.79 GHz with V_{t2} from 0.6 V to 1.4 V, respectively. The simulated and measured oscillation frequencies with only one tuning voltage, *i.e.*, $V_{t1} = V_{t2} = V_t$, for real applications particularly in the phase-locked loop (PLL) are plotted in Fig. 14b. A FBW of 9.03% is achieved in measurement, whereas it is of 5.8% with only tuning the varactors in the LC -tank in this design. A deviation of maximum 4% is observed between the simulated and measured oscillation frequency. This may be caused by the overestimated capacitance values in simulations. The frequency tuning does not show any gap for adjacent tuning voltage settings in simulations and measurements, and thus, a continuous TR is ensured. The increased measured FBW compared to the theoretical results is caused by the frequency-dependent behavior of the capacitances. The output power including the cable and probe losses is -8 dBm in

Fig. 14. (a) Measured oscillation frequency, and (b) continuous TR of the VCO with $V_{t1} = V_{t2} = V_t$.

Fig. 15. Measured spectral curves at maximum and minimum oscillation frequency.

measurements with its variation less than 1 dB over the entire tuning voltage settings. The measured spectral curves at the maximum and minimum oscillation frequency are shown in Fig. 15. The actual output power of the VCO is -1.4 dBm after de-embedding the cable loss of 5.6 dB and the probe loss of 1 dB according to measurement and the datasheet, respectively.

Phase noise measurements are carried out with the same measurement setup and the built-in function of the spectrum analyzer for phase noise measurement is used. Fig. 16 shows the measured phase noise at four different oscillation frequencies as representatives. The VCO provides a phase noise of -114.6 dBc/Hz at 10-MHz offset with small deviations

TABLE IV
COMPARISON WITH STATE-OF-THE-ART CONTINUOUSLY TUNING VCOS

Reference	Technology	Supply (V)	P_{DC}^+ (mW)	Continuous TR (GHz)	FBW (%)	Phase noise ⁺⁺ (dBc/Hz)	Size (mm ²)	FOM _T [*]
MWCL'22 [21]	22-nm FD-SOI	1	14.4	23.6 - 24.4	3.3	-122.4	0.026 [#]	-168.8
MWCL'21 [22]	90-nm CMOS	0.6	7.08	27.5 - 30.04	8.83	-111.5	0.42	-171.1
MWCL'16 [23]	90-nm CMOS	1.2	6	23.7 - 24.9	4.9	-122	0.02 [#]	-175.7
TMTT'23 [24]	90-nm SiGe BiCMOS	2.3	24.7	27.9 - 28.8	3.2	-130	0.09 [#]	-175.2
BCICTS'23 [1]	130-nm SiGe BiCMOS	1.5	27	30.4 - 32.9	7.89	-116	1.02	-169.6
ISCAS'18 [25]	130-nm SiGe BiCMOS	2.7	69.4	26.9 - 27.2	1.2	-127	0.48	-158.8
This work	130-nm SiGe BiCMOS	0.83	10.1	29.6 - 32.4	9.03	-114.6	0.5	-173.5

^{*} Core. ⁺⁺ Measured at 10-MHz offset. [#] Excludes pads.

$$* \text{FOM}_T = \mathcal{L}(\Delta\omega) - 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{\omega_o}{\Delta\omega}\right) + 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{P_{DC}}{1 \text{ mW}}\right) - 20 \cdot \log\left(\frac{\text{FBW}(\%)}{10\%}\right).$$

Fig. 16. Simulated and measured phase noise of the VCO.

for different tuning voltage settings in measurements. The simulated phase noise plotted in Fig. 16 is obtained from full EM simulations of the VCO in Keysight ADS with Momentum EM for the purpose of comparison. The difference of simulated phase noise at 1-MHz offset between the minimum and maximum oscillation frequency is presented because of thermal noise contributions of Q_3 and Q_4 at different tuning voltage settings. The contribution of shot noise and flicker noise are not significant compared to thermal noise according to simulations. Difference between measured and simulated phase-noise results can be attributed to the underestimation of flicker noise contribution of the transistors, and AM-to-PM noise from the supply voltages.

A comparison with state-of-the-art continuously tuning VCOS with a similar frequency range is made in Table IV. Typically for the VCOS in SiGe technologies, higher supply voltages and power consumption are required compared to CMOS designs, whereas in this work a comparable supply voltage of 0.83 V is applied and the power consumption especially at low tuning voltage settings is close to that of CMOS designs. By taking into account base parasitics and introducing varactors in the cross-feedback path of the class-C topology, the proposed VCO releases the TR limitation by the LC -tank and provides the highest continuous TR among all designs, and the most pronounced FOM_T in 130-nm SiGe BiCMOS

technology. The phase noise performance is comparable to that of other class-C designs in the same frequency range in SiGe BiCMOS. The low-DC-power, high-TR, and low-phase-noise characteristics make this design suitable for high-performance frequency synthesizer systems.

V. CONCLUSION

Parasitic capacitances and the C_{max}/C_{min} -ratio of varactors dominate the achievable TR of a VCO. In this paper the effect of introducing varactors in the cross-feedback path of a class-C VCO on TR is analytically discussed in the presence of parasitic capacitances, and experimentally verified by a fabricated VCO consisting of varactors in the LC -tank as well as the cross-feedback path. The analysis of startup and phase noise in the presence of base parasitics is given as design fundamentals of the proposed VCO. Measurement results showcase an improved TR while keeping very low DC power consumption and good phase noise. In the implementation, a new varactor is proposed to achieve higher C_{max}/C_{min} , and a specific capacitor placement is used for its symmetrical property and compactness.

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